

A PERSPECTIVE ON SADRIDDIN AINI'S CREATIVE WORK
AND THE ROLE OF HIS SCHOLARLY LEGACY IN STUDYING
OUR RECENT HISTORY

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Abstract. This article scientifically analyzes the life, scientific and literary heritage of the historian and literary scholar Sadriddin Aini, his scientific and creative activity as a poet, translator, historian, source, orientalist, novelist, scientist and publicist. In addition, the article contains information about Sadriddin Aini's contemporaries who wrote memoirs about his scientific and creative activity, scientific heritage, Jadeedism and development, as well as "History of Bukhara Mangit Amirs", "Materials for the history of the Bukhara Revolution", "Samples of Tajik literature", "Memoirs" and other important issues on the history of Bukhara and Turkestan.

Key words: Madrasa, mudarris, "Esdaliklar", education, textbook, ablution, fasting, funeral, hajj, zakat, marriage, divorce, trade, meditation, poetry

Аннотация. В данной статье научно проанализированы научно-творческая деятельность, публицистическое творчество историк-автора, выдающегося мастера слов, литератора Садриддина Айнаи как поэт, переводчик, историограф, источниковед, востоковед, учёный на основе сведений современников и близких ему людей. Изучены мнения и воспоминания соеремеников Садриддина Айнаи о его научном наследии, джадидской и просветительской деятельности, а также о произведениях "История мангытских эмиров Бухары", "Материалы для истории Бухарской

революции", "Образцы таджикской литературы", "Воспоминания" и о значении, сведения этих произведений по истории Бухары и Туркестана.

Ключевые слова: медресе, мударрис, Воспоминания, образование, учебник, омовение, пост, похороны, хадж, закят, брак, талок (развод).

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada, tarixnavis adib, yirik soʻz sanʼatkori va adabiyotshunos olim Sadridin Ayniyning hayot yoʻli, ilmiy-adabiy merosi shoir, tarjimon, tarixshunos, manbashunos, sharqshunos, romannavis, olim sifatidagi ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyati, publisistik ijodi, uning zamondoshlari va yaqin qalam ahllari tomonidan Sadridin Ayniyning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyati, ilmiy merosiga, jadidchilik va taraqqiyparvarlik faoliyatiga oʻz asarlarida, u haqdagi fikr-mulohazalarini va xotiralari toʻgʻrisidagi maʼlumotlar, shuningdek, "Buxoro mangʻit amirlari tarixi", "Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar", "Tojik adabiyotidan namunalar", "Esdaliklar" kabi asarlarining mazmun-mohiyati, uning ushbu asarlarida Buxoro va Turkiston tarixi boʻyicha tilga olingan muhim tarixiy, ijtimoiy-madaniy masalalar ilmiy jihatdan tahlil etilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Madrasa, mudarris, Esdaliklar, taʼlim, darslik tahorat, roʻza, janoza, haj, zakot, nikoh, taloq, savdo-sotiq, tafakkur, sheʼr.

Special attention was paid to our history after our state gained independence. the contribution of Turkestan thinker allomas to the development of Science, who lived and worked in our past in the development of not only political, economic, social spheres, but also in the development of spiritual educational spheres, the socio-political life of Muslim countries in the late 19th - early 20th century, the emergence of the Jadid movement and the role and social President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's visit to Bukhara in 2018, indeed, no matter how many trials and tribulations in the past, the river of Science, Culture and art of Bukharoi Sharif has never stopped. The instructive life of the devotees of the Enlightenment, such as Ahmad Donish, Abdurauf Fitrat, Fayzulla Khojaev, Sadridin Ayniy, who was born and created in this great land, is still today the

establishment of a new society in our country, the upbringing of a harmonious generation

Historiography, the major work of the artist Sadriiddin Ayniy (1878-1954) wrote down in his historical, artistic works a number of important issues important in his major works such as “Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar”, “Namunai adabiyoti tochik” (“Tojik adabiyoti namunalari”) and “Esdaliklar” about the pen-dwellers of the historians, scholars, poets, educated, intellectuals of his time in general.

Ayniy's famous work “Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar”, published in 1926 in Moscow, Uzbek, (Arabic spelling), occupies a large place in the writer's work. In this historical-literary study, the author spoke with respect and reverence the scientific - creative activities of Bukharian representatives of spirituality and enlightenment, such as Ahmad Donish, Isa Mahdum, Sharifjan Mahdum (Sadri Ziyoy), Qori Abdulmajid Zufunun, Mirzo Abdulazim Somi Boastani, Afzal Mahdum Pirmasti Bukhari, Mirzo Abdulvohid Munzim, Mir Muhammad Siddiq Hashmat Bukhari, Yahyokhaja, Abdullakhoja Abdi, Mullah Sharifi clock and Abdurauf Fitrat.

Wanting the knowledge of the famous scientist, not satisfied with the old school lessons, his old educational methods, he ensured that he studied in Bukhara madrasas. Ayniy lived for nearly thirty years (1889 - 1917)

Held in Bukhara. The enlightened scholar studied in the famous and well-known Bukhara madrasas of the time Miri Arab (1890-1891), Olimjon (1892-1893), Badalbek (1894-1896), Hoji Zahid (1896-1899) and Kokaldosh (1899-1900). He witnessed many historical events live. He got acquainted with famous scientists, poets and famous science lovers of this period, established scientific and creative and literary cooperation.

It was from this period that his contemporaries and close pen-men, indifferent to Ayniy's scientific and creative activity and scientific heritage, to the work of jadidism and progressivism, wrote down and objectively assessed his thoughts and

memories of him in their works. In particular, Abdullakhoja Abdiy's "Shuaroi mutaaxxirini Buxoro", which in the ranks of the figures of the literary and historical environment of that time mentioned Ayni with reverence and sincerity, characterizes him in the manner of "an intelligent, knowledgeable, rare thinker", while Afzal Mahdum Pirmastiy Bukhari's "Afzal - ut-tazkor fikr-ush-shuaro v-Al-ash'or" (1904), compiled in 1904 "Ayniy Sadridin-xoja adabiyotshunos va talantli shoir, noyob iste" "dod sohibidir", while idrishkhoja in Roji's" Bayaz "(1907), Mir Muhammad Siddiq Hashmat in Bukhari's "Tazkirat-ut-shuaro", in tazkiralaras, expressed warm thoughts about Ayni's talent as a poet.

Ayniy work and scientific legacy have attracted the attention of many researchers. Haji Muin Shukrullo (1883-1942), an Uzbek national intellectual, was one of the first in his time to give an impartial assessment of Ayni's educational-historical views, printing activities, images of historical processes in his works, especially "Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar", a major work of Ayniy. Also, Haji Muin singled out the services of the scientist towards the development of National Press in Samarkand: for a while, the translation and editing works of the newspaper " "Mehnatkashlar tovushi" were served by Saidrizo Alizadeh, Muhammadjan Yusufiy, Qori Muhammadrahim Toji, Sadridin Ayniy Afandi. Among these, the one who worked a long (long) term at the first level was undoubtedly the same afandi. Khabir, the editor of the "Bolalar yo'ldoshi" "Shu" "lai inqilob" (magazine) complex, was the son of Abdurashid Abdujabbor, the head in charge. This is a clear message in the editorial board

Ayniy, with the famous statesman Fayzulla Khojaev (1896-1938), will be in friendly and creative cooperation for many years. On his advice and recommendation, Ayniy's work "Qizbola yoki Xolida", composed in Uzbek for the girls ' school, will be published in 1924 in Uzbek at the "Kamyoviniy" printing house (with the participation and assistance of Abdulvohid Munzim) in Berlin, as well as in Moscow in 1926, a large literary study and anthology, "Namunai adabiyoti tojik" ("samples of Tajik literature"). The work "Qizbola yoki Xolida" is

a literary and moral book and is the first book for a women's school to come out in Uzbek.

F.Kho‘jayev in his work “materials on the history of the Bukharan revolution”, khojaev also gave a worthy assessment of Ayniy's scientific and creative activity, his views on jadidism and progressivism. F.Kho‘jayev having carefully studied the books and articles written by khojaev Ayniy on the history of the Bukharan revolution, he correctly shows their achievements and shortcomings in time. Chunonchi, reflecting on Ayni's “Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar”, writes: “1921-1922 on this topic came out Ayni's book “Buxoro inqilobi tarixi uchun materiallar”. Aynius worked from the Zuhur of jadidism, and was both its leader and one of its founders. Ayni's work contains materials of great value, which depict some periods of the jadidist movement. The work is particularly interesting in spirit, and beautifully depicts some leaders of the jadidist movement, and Ayny among them, the life and feelings he has lived”.

In 1921-1923, during Ayny's tenure as a consultant to the Consulate of the Bukhara people's Soviet republic in Samarkand, the government of the BPR quits using the creative rise of the writer Ayny. Personally, F.Under the leadership of khojaev, on September 13, 1923, the following decision will be made about Ayniy: “taking into account the services of Comrade Ayniy in the revolution movement and his long - standing activities for the benefit of the Bukharan working masses, the Bukharan MIK faction will be offered to assign him a personal pension in the amount of the 17-discharge rate with Let the secretariat be entrusted with a letter to Comrade Aynius, after which he is asked to devote himself exclusively to literary activities.”

Abdurauf Fitrat (1886-1938), a famous exponent of the Bukharan jadidism movement, writer, playwright, orator and poet, was also not indifferent to the work of his contemporary Ayniy. Fitrat wrote a foreword to Adib's “Odina”, first published in Tajik in 1927, and warmly congratulated Ayni on this work, acknowledging that it was a valuable and important work. Aynius also cited

several poems from Fitrat's collection when he composed his “Namunai adabiyoti tojik” , citing Fitrat as the founder of 20th-century Persian-Tajik poetry.

In conclusion, it can be said that contemporaries who created in their time in the same period as Aynius, who were not indifferent to his work, gave a worthy assessment of the achievements and shortcomings of the scientist in science. Directly, Aeneas also kept in close contact, writing scientific, social and literary articles and large-small works about his contemporaries.

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